

METAL - COMPOSITE LAMINATES FOR EFFICIENT ENERGY ABSORBING SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The energy absorbing capability of SMC when combined with a variety of sheet materials in laminate form has been investigated. It was found that considerable improvements in the energy absorption of SMC could be induced by combining the material with a stiff backing layer. It was also found that the deformation characteristics of the backing layer were relevant to the energy absorption of the SMC and that ductile substrates capable of supporting extensive deformation are required.

INTRODUCTION

Combinations of sheet metals and fibre-reinforced plastics to form macrocomposite laminates have been evaluated to assess their potential as efficient energy absorbing systems. Preliminary results were obtained for sheet moulding compound, SMC, laminated with 0.6 mm stainless steel (1). It was found that the energy absorption capacity of SMC increases significantly when it is laminated with steel and impacts occur on the SMC surface.

A simple interpretation of the observed results might suggest that the increased energy absorption achieved in the SMC was a result of a modified distribution of stress within the material during impact. The stiffness of the steel layer would ensure that the neutral axis of the system was contained within, or close to, the steel such that the SMC was primarily loaded in compression and thereby capable of sustaining a greater density of microcracking before catastrophic failure than a comparable sheet of SMC tested in isolation where high tensile stress would develop.

The initial investigation was extended to include other materials laminated with the SMC in order to test this simple hypothesis. These alternative materials consisted of aluminium alloys with differing strengths and a polymeric ionomer.

In the initial phase of the study the ultimate energy absorbing capabilities of the SMC-steel macrocomposite could not be assessed due to limitations on the load capacity of the impact facilities. Further tests were performed on the SMC-steel systems using a machine with increased capacity in order to perform fully penetrating impacts.

The objective of this paper is to provide answers to the following questions:-

- 1) What is the ultimate energy absorbing capabilities of a steel-SMC macrocomposite?
- 2) What is the maximum energy that may be absorbed by the SMC itself during impact (as part of a macrocomposite)?
- 3) What are the necessary requirements for the other layer of a macrocomposite in order to realise this optimal energy absorption?

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

All impact testing was performed on square specimens, 60 mm by 60 mm, cut from laminated sheets of SMC and either stainless steel, relatively pure aluminium, S1C, an aluminium alloy, L156 or a polymeric ionomer. The SMC thickness was either 2, 4, 6 or 8 mm while the stainless steel thicknesses were 0.6, 1 and 2mm. The two aluminium systems were 0.6mm thick and the ionomer was 4mm thick.

The impact test consisted of supporting the plates on a steel ring, 40 mm in diameter, and striking them with an instrumented steel tup with a hemispherical striker, of diameter 20 mm. For the majority of tests the impact fixture was mounted in a falling weight impact frame with the incident impact energy controlled by raising or lowering the drop height of the striker. In a more limited series of tests aimed at achieving full penetration of the SMC-steel laminates, the fixture was mounted in a servo hydraulic machine with a ram capable of traveling upwards at speed of 1 - 5 M/s and equipped with a load cell,

capacity 200 KN. . The signal produced by the load cell after impact was fed to an oscilloscope which was itself connected to an X-Y recorder and the force - displacement was obtained. Although the latter tests constituted a driven rather than a falling dart , no differences were observed in the results for forces and displacements during impacts performed on SMC sheets tested to full penetration on both machines . Macrocomposite laminates were simply supported during impact but impacts performed on thin metal sheet required light clamping of the specimens to avoid folding of the specimen into the support orifice and to reproduce the deformation profile observed when the metal was combined with SMC .

Impacts were performed at speeds ranging from 1-5m/s at room temperature ,16-20 °C.

RESULTS

The failure mode of the lightly clamped stainless steel specimens regardless of their thicknesses (0.6 , 1 and 2 mm) were all similar involving the formation of a dome that ruptured with a flap (fig. 1a). A similar failure occurred when the steel was combined with the SMC , figure 1b at all combinations of steel and SMC thicknesses The force deflection curves for 6 mm SMC with a layer of stainless steel (0.6 , 1 and 2 mm) are shown in figure 2. The curves consist of an initial steep rise portion followed by a transition to a curve of lower slope before a maximum is reached. The initial peak (P_i) is the point at which the layer of stainless steel yields (1).

Figure 1 : Stainless steel and SMC-stainless steel specimens after complete penetration a) stainless steel; b) SMC-stainless steel viewed from the steel side c) SMC-stainless steel viewed from SMC side.

Figure 2 : Force deflection curves for 6 mm SMC with three different thicknesses of stainless steel after total penetration.

The maximum energy absorbed by the laminates with varying combinations of SMC and steel thicknesses were obtained from the area under the force-displacement curves and are shown in fig 3 . The energy absorbed by the SMC itself as part of the macrocomposite may be derived using an approach, outlined in a previous paper (1), in which the deformation of the steel is measured . The energy required to deform the steel to a particular extent is obtained from slow tests on steel sheet and this quantity is subtracted from the total energy absorbed by the laminate. The results of this exercise for SMC in combination with each of the three thicknesses of steel are plotted in figure 4 as a function of SMC thickness , together with a comparable set of results for SMC tested in isolation .

Figure 3 : Maximum energy absorbed by the laminate for different thicknesses of SMC as a function of stainless steel thickness.

The SMC-aluminium systems were tested and examined in much the same way as for SMC-stainless steel. Analysis of the energy absorbed by the various constituents indicated that any macrocomposite effect (i.e. increase in energy absorption by SMC) was negligible with this combination. Results obtained from testing L156 laminates were slightly better than those from the S1C but the improvements are of the order of a few percent and are not significant . Figure 5 shows derived data indicating the energy absorbed by the SMC layer in a SMC-aluminium (S1C) laminate compared to the energy absorbed by SMC on its own with the SMC layer being 4mm thick in each case . The results were obtained from specimens subjected to progressively greater incident impact energies up to those required for complete penetration .. It can be seen that the energy absorbed by the SMC in the laminates is similar to that absorbed by SMC of a similar thickness tested in isolation . A single representative datum for the SMC-aluminium (L156) is shown for clarity . It is interesting to note that limited test results obtained from testing the SMC-ionomer laminate did reveal a significant improvement although not of the same magnitude as that exhibited by SMC-steel . The single datum shown in figure 5 for this system indicates a maximum energy absorption of some 70-75J . The equivalent values for a steel substrate would be 110 -125J .

DISCUSSION

The results have showed that an SMC layer in a SMC-stainless steel laminate absorbs more energy than SMC of a similar thickness can when tested in isolation. Stainless steel has a high Young's modulus (210 GPa), whereas SMC has a Young's modulus that ranges from 10 GPa in the plane of the laminate to about 5 GPa through the thickness. Therefore, allowing for the relative thicknesses of the two layers, the effect of the stiff steel layer will be to place most of the SMC under compression during the initial stages of loading and to reduce the tensile stress experienced by the brittle composite . For the case of the thinner SMC layers and the thicker steel layers it is probable that the neutral axis would be placed within the steel layer itself ensuring that the SMC did not experience any tensile forces at all during the initial loading sequence .

Figure 4 : Maximum energy absorption as a function of thickness for SMC and SMC as a layer in macrocomposite (SMC') for all thicknesses of steel tested from 0.6 mm to 2 mm.

The stiffening of the laminate by the steel (2,3) would however result in high contact stresses at the surface of the SMC in contact with the impactor .This in itself would increase the energy absorbed by the SMC during the failure process by inducing extensive cracking in the upper surface of the SMC before tensile cracking had occurred at the opposite face. A parallel could be drawn with the accepted model for energy absorption in armour plate systems where a ceramic such as Al_2O_3 is supported by a stiff, strong backing plate.It is assumed in such cases that failure is dominated by compressive cracking induced by a projectile which passes through the material by a process analogous to wear .

The observation that the maximum energy that may be absorbed by SMC in a steel -SMC macrocomposite is apparently independent of steel thickness , figure 4 , would indeed suggest that the prime role of the metal layer is to place the SMC largely in compression , whereupon a modified failure process occurs which is characteristic of the material . The single datum that is shown in figure 4 that does not lie on the common curve is one for the case of a thin steel layer (0.6 mm) and a relatively thick SMC layer (6mm) where it could be argued that the steel layer is simply not stiff enough relative to the SMC to prevent significant tensile stresses developing in the SMC .

A study of the cracking pattern in an SMC-steel laminate after partial failure does not however totally support this interpretation . Fig 6 shows micrographs of two sections , one taken through an SMC specimen and the other an SMC-steel specimen after both had been subjected to similar non-catastrophic impacts .The cracking pattern in the SMC specimen clearly indicates that fracture is developing at the tensile face as expected . The section of the SMC-steel specimen does not however reveal cracking concentrated at the compressive face of the SMC .Instead the cracking is distributed relatively evenly throughout the section and is comprised mainly of delaminations .

The results of the aluminium-SMC tests also fail to support the concept of a stiff metal being the requirement for improved energy absorption . Although the aluminium alloys have a Young's modulus of 70 Gpa which is well below that of steel they are substantially stiffer than the SMC and an

improvement in the energy absorbing character of the SMC might have been expected, particularly with the thinner layers of the composite. Amongst the most interesting results were those obtained with the ionomer as the substrate layer. The ionomer was a very flexible plastic system with a low modulus of 0.3 Gpa, but the comparatively thick layer used, 4mm, provided a bending stiffness equivalent to that of the 0.6mm aluminium. In this case the substrate did provide an increase in energy absorption in the SMC although not of the same magnitude as that achieved in the steel-SMC macrocomposites.

Figure 5 : Absorbed energy vs impact energy for a range of alternative macrocomposite systems based on 4 mm thick SMC.

In order to explain these observed trends it is necessary to look beyond the stiffness of the layers and consider the general deformation characteristics of the steel, aluminium and ionomer. The steel and the ionomer are ductile materials that are capable of extensive deformation during the impact test. The aluminium systems in contrast are relatively brittle under the biaxial loading regime induced during impact and fracture at a deflection similar to that of the SMC sheets tested in isolation. It is likely therefore that, while it is important for the substrate layer to be stiff enough to place a significant fraction of the SMC in compression during the initial stages of the impact test, it is also important for the material to be able to support the SMC over a deformation range significantly beyond that normally achieved on its own. The cracking pattern evident in figure 6b therefore reflects the deformation processes occurring during the later stages of the impact where a situation more closely resembling membrane stressing will have been established in the laminate which has been forced to conform to the profile of the impactor. The mechanism of energy absorption in these macrocomposites is therefore not analogous to that postulated for ceramic based armour plate but a characteristic of the combination of a fibre reinforced composite with a ductile, stiff, substrate.

CONCLUSIONS

When an appropriate backing layer or substrate is chosen to form a macrocomposite with a fibre-reinforced composite such as SMC, the SMC absorbs considerably more energy than is possible if it is tested in isolation. Furthermore, the maximum energy that may be absorbed by SMC under such conditions is a characteristic property of the material, independent of the thickness of this backing layer.

The two requirements of the backing layer are that it is both stiff in order to place the SMC into compression in the initial stages of deformation and ductile in order to support the SMC during the later stages of deformation. Note that these requirements relate to the substrate as a structure and are accordingly not material property requirements.

Figure 6 : Cross section through specimens after comparable non-penetrating impacts
a) (at top) SMC , b) (at bottom) SMC-stainless steel.

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